

Alliance Data Officers' Group Meeting

Thursday 28th of September 2023 1pm to 2:30pm

This is a summary of the key outcomes and actions from the quarterly UK Health Data Research Alliance Data Officers' Group (DOG).

Summary of Actions

Action	Lead	Outcome
Update and clarity will be given from the Alliance executive committee, on the federated data platform and the sub national SDEs created by NHS England.	Alliance Team	The FDP has been announced: NHS England » Data platform FAQs The Alliance Community Bulletin for November included links to the announcement and to responses from AMRC and HDR UK: https://ukhealthdata.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Alliance-community-bulletin-November-2023.pdf
Speakers' slides will be made available for people who are interested.	Alliance team	Presentations are linked from this document.

1. Welcome

The Chair (Geoff Hall) welcomed all, especially after the long gap since the last Data Officers' group meeting in February 2023.

2. Alliance update – Paola Quattroni

Alliance update

The Alliance continues to convene health research organisations to drive best practice in health data. We recently extended [membership](#) to Trade Associations, Public groups, and non-data custodians, and recently welcomed the Association of British Pharmaceutical Industry (ABPI), Association of Medical Research Charities and Understanding Patient Data.

Alliance Executive Committee

An Alliance Executive Committee has been set up to provide steer on prioritisation of Alliance activities, reporting into the Alliance Council. Currently chaired by David Seymour, members include:

- Michael Chapman (NHS England)
- Alex Newberry (Welsh government)
- Roger Halliday (Research Data Scotland)
- Ian Young (Health and Social Care Northern Ireland)
- Jan Speechley (Public contributor)
- Nicola Perrin (AMRC)
- Janet Valentine (ABPI)
- Andrew Morris (HDR UK)
- Jan Speechley (Public contributor)
- Richard Ballerand (Public contributor)

Alliance working groups

Technology:

- **Secure Data Environment (SDE) integration working group.** The HDR UK technology team have been convening members across the NHS England (NHSE) SDE network to facilitate integration with the Innovation Gateway, focussing on metadata onboarding and data discovery, and developing SDE Gateway collections.

Trust & Transparency:

- We currently launched a [funding call](#) for data custodians (offering up to £15,000) to implement transparency standards for health data access processes in research. Nineteen projects have been [awarded](#) funding and will be completed by the end of March 2024.

Usable data:

- Work on adoption of the Observational Medical Outcome Partnership (OMOP) common data model is continuing through partnership with NHS, OHDSI and through the OMOP Special Interest Group.
- **Clinical Trials prioritisation forum:** This group is convened by the Alliance and chaired by Matt Sydes and Marion Mafham, with the aim to discuss barriers to effective use of healthcare systems data (HSD) in clinical trials, how these can be addressed, and to prioritise the necessary actions to realise these potential benefits. This forum would facilitate an exchange of ideas between data providers, consumers of trial results and the clinical trials community. This includes prioritising, providing, endorsing, or commissioning research and/or practical guidance on obtaining and using HSD efficiently, with internationally reliable interpretability.

Capacity building:

1. Black internship programme: in the last round, we had 93 interns across 54 organisations, 20 of which were Alliance members. Internships concluded at the end of August.
2. The Association of Professional Health Care Analysts (AphA) have recently written a letter to Amanda Pritchard, Chief Executive of NHS England (also shared with Steve Barclay and Wes Streeting) to express their concern at the absence of analysts from the NHS Long Term Workforce Plan. They believe it is a symptomatic of a failure to really address the current data and analytical needs of the health and care services. The full letter is [here](#).

3. Insights from Sudlow review, with focus on data priorities – Lynn Morrice (BHF Data Science Centre)

[\[Link to presentation file “Alliance Data officers Sudlow Review slides 28Sept2023.pdf”\]](#) Led by Prof. Cathie Sudlow, Chief Scientist at HR UK, the Sudlow review will explore the UK health data flows and how they can be improved for public benefit in healthcare. It is supported by the UK’s 4 CMOs, the Chief Statistician and the NHSE director for transformation and will focus on:

- Mapping linkable health data sets across the UK, and
- Outlining the barriers and solutions to sharing and linking data for public benefit (focussed on England)
- What data flows need to be prioritised and enabled to support health and care planning, population insights and research?
- What are the barriers to enabling these priority health data flows and linkage in the UK?
- What are the solutions for unlocking these barriers and realising the potential of health data in the UK?
- Data that is in-scope includes data collected at national level from NHS in the 4 UK nations at population scale, e.g. secondary care, medication, as well as more locally collected NHS data like free-text notes and imaging. Also in scope are Health-relevant data from non-NHS organisations (e.g., ADR UK, ONS, SAIL Databank, RDS; census education and social care).
- Other data, which is not in scope but will be referred to includes personal monitoring information, environmental data and research generated data. Linkage to these data sets can enhance the insights from the in-scope data sets.

Some of the emerging priorities include:

- Data priorities:
 - availability of and access to **primary care**, social care, national audits and registries, medicines, screening, non-NHS health-relevant data (cross-sectoral linkages), laboratory data, hospital admissions in near real-time, hospital out-patient, images and free text.
- System priorities:
 - maintain broader access beyond COVID; build and maintain trust (ongoing, meaningful PPIE)
 - streamline & standardise governance and access
 - simplify and avoid unnecessary duplication
 - maintain and enhance national data solutions
 - maintain and extend secure ‘data dissemination’ route for ‘consented’ cohorts and trials
 - enhance cross-sectoral data linkage and access; Increase capacity – IG and data engineering; embed partnership working (academia /industry/ NHS).
- Coding and data standards were identified as particular issues for data usability; missing data also found to be an issue.
- Insights from the Sudlow review will be published in the coming weeks. If anyone wishes to discuss the Sudlow review or provide case studies, please contact Lynn.Morrice@hdruk.ac.uk

4. Surveying the landscape of OMOP CDM adoption in the UK – Alex Knight (UK Health Data Research Alliance)

[\[Link to presentation “OMOP survey results.pdf”\]](#)

The Health Data Research Alliance is supporting OMOP CDM¹ adoption in the UK.

- The EHDEN² IMI³ Project, which supported [187 data custodians across Europe](#) (22 from the UK) to transform their data to OMOP and make it available for research, has nearly finished. The DARWIN-EU⁴ project is generating RWE⁵ at scale for the EMA⁶.
- OMOP has been [selected as the first common data model](#) by the NHSE Research Secure Data Environment network
- OHDSI⁷ is the SDO⁸ for the OMOP CDM, with >3,000 collaborators in 80 countries
- A Good example is the paper from Voss *et al.* [eClinicalMedicine (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.101932> “Adverse events of special interest (AESIs) for COVID-19 infection and vaccines”]. Study had 493 M “Control” Patients!
- The Alliance is supporting OMOP adoption through: funding of 5 EHDEN partners to transform their data to OMOP; convening a special interest group for OMOP; supporting OHDSI UK node; curating community resources; partnership with NHSE to support adoption of standards in the SDE network and facilitate discoverability of data in the HDR UK innovation gateway; and surveying the landscape of OMOP.
 - The OMOP survey, explores organisations adopting OMOP, data custodians and data users, the challenges, tools used, types of data mapped to OMOP and continuity of Mapping to OMOP. The results are currently being analysed. However, the preliminary report is available and can be found [here](#); poster is [here](#). Organisations across the UK are currently involved in OMOP transformation activities. For example 2 of 4 Scottish regional safe havens (HIC⁹ and DataLoch) have OMOP-mapped their data sets.
 - Lancashire Teaching Hospitals and DataLoch are exploring potential collaboration on OMOP.
 - The Scottish Government (as part of their strategy for data-driven care) have started work on developing an Information Governance Code of Conduct in relation to Health and Social Care data, based upon the ICO guidance and for their eventual review and approval. [This is a link](#) to the initial executive summary outlining the IG Review across the Health and Social Care sector in Scotland.

¹ Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model: <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

² European Health Data & Evidence Network: <https://www.ehden.eu/>

³ The Innovative Medicines Initiative (<https://www.imi.europa.eu/>) is a European funding programme

⁴ Data Analysis and Real-World Interrogation Network (<https://www.darwin-eu.org/>)

⁵ Real World Evidence

⁶ European Medicines Agency (<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en>)

⁷ Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (pronounced "Odyssey": <https://www.ohdsi.org/>)

⁸ Standards Development Organisation

⁹ Health Informatics Centre (<https://www.dundee.ac.uk/hic>)

- Health and Social Care (HSC) Northern Ireland have been involved in the [CO-CONNECT](#) project, OMOP may become more prominent in the next few years as part of the implementation of the HSC Data Strategy/Information Institute.
- Generation Scotland data was also processed by Co-Connect.

5. Research Data Scotland Synthetic data strategy – Lynne Adair (RDS)

[\[Link to presentation “RDS Synthetic data short intro.pdf”\]](#)

- RDS’s mission is unlocking public sector data to support research. Synthetic data work is supporting this remit. Looking at mainly health and government data (such as census and education data).
- Using synthetic data to support researchers in advance of them accessing data, in terms of data discovery, training and code development.
- So far, we have been scoping the synthetic data landscape, and developing a synthetic data strategy.
- Workstreams on disclosure risk and information governance; synthesis; and access, promotion, and engagement.
- A project was recently funded for disclosure risk and Information governance (IG) to create advice for data controllers on how to evaluate disclosure risk from synthetic data.
- Some works have been funded to explore and investigate different types of synthetic data tools, including the Synthpop tool which RDS will be taking forward. Regional safe havens doing test syntheses of data sets. Pilot synthesis work on pupil census.
- User engagement workshops feedback was to begin with generation of low fidelity datasets and managing Information governance challenges. Public engagement feedback was a mixture of support and concerns, and the main outcome was to better describe the benefits, and control usage by not making synthetic data publicly available.
- Funding for tools, disclosure risk and example data sets – looking to fund further synthetic data projects. Related resources: <https://github.com/Project-MONAI/GenerativeModels>; <https://synthea.mitre.org/>

6. Update from the SDE Data and Technology Working Group – Tim Hubbard

- The Data for R&D programme of NHS England aims to implement the vision of providing access to data across a federated network of secure data environments (SDEs), rather than distributing data. £200M funding has been initially allocated for the set-up of 11 sub-national SDEs.
- The programme is based on the 42 integrated care systems in England, which bring together NHS GPs, hospitals, community care, social care, and involving local government. There will be regional secure data environments which will hold this data, for research access and other types of analyst access for health service.
- There are set of communities of practice to coordinate the SDEs, share expertise and reach consensus about ways of operation. The various workstreams include technology and data, information governance, PPIE, communications and engagement, commercial and academic access.
- There is also the national SDE – less granular data.

- It has been agreed that all the sub-national SDEs will work towards OMOP as an interoperability data standard. There is still ongoing discussion about information governance processes.
- It's been decided that the HDR gateway will provide a single front door for discovery of data held by the SDEs. The aim is to Make it easier to discover data sets, simplify the data access processes, and facilitate federated cohort discovery.
- The Federated Data Platform has been [announced](#). The FDP was procured to support hospital management on live data, but not research, so it is different in application from the SDEs (although some of the SDEs will also support local management use).
- 5 AI centres – funding coming to an end – should be connected to the SDEs.

During the discussion, questions were raised about need for clarity around the use of data in the FDP and the SDEs, and the level of interoperability between the two platforms. It was stressed that one of the benefits of the sub-national SDEs is to support local innovation, however SDEs will also be used to support business intelligence and operations, therefore interoperability will be important. Work is also ongoing with Integrated Care Boards (ICBs) to ensure sustainability beyond 2025 (when the Data for R&D programme should conclude).

7. Smart Data Research UK– Deborah Kroll, Bruce Jackson

[\[Link to presentation “SDRUK - simple overview.pdf”\]](#)

- Smart Data Research UK aims to enable researchers to generate new insights using the wealth of data that people generate through everyday interactions with the digital world (e.g. satellites, navigation, retail, social media, financial, apps, wearables, IoT...).
- The UK has done pioneering work using smart data and there is huge potential, but the data is not widely available and there are not always the technical capabilities to work with it.
- A landscape analysis has highlighted: difficulties finding the data, leading to duplication of effort and inefficient use of time; bilateral licences requiring siloed working and hindering the re-use of data, replication of studies, and enrichment of data through linking. Because researchers don't have access to shared data, there is limited potential to develop and evaluate methods and tools for working with these data sources, as well as ethical standards and robust governance that would be driven by real use cases. Companies do not have robust ways of vetting researchers, which is a security risk.
- The Consumer Data Research Centre and Urban Big Data Centre) as well as an accelerator scheme are conducting pilot research.

The cancer loyalty card study is a case study funded by Cancer Research UK, exploring how a high street retailer's loyalty card data could reduce the delays in diagnosis among women who are experiencing symptoms associated with ovarian cancer. This study is based on consented data sharing and linkage to a survey, with a big public involvement and engagement element. The findings showed that purchases of medications for pain and indigestion were greater in women diagnosed with ovarian cancer up to 8 months prior to diagnosis. Patients were potentially managing their symptoms for about four months with over-the-counter medication before they sought help from a GP, and this came through that loyalty card data.

- This study is an example of the complexity that comes from a study with “smart data”.

- Smart Data Research UK programmes will invest ~60M in digital research infrastructure for new data services, a central hub, ethics and legal service, public engagement, and a flexible fund for innovative research.

Relevant resources:

<https://engagementhub.ukri.org/esrc-strategic-hub/smart-data-research-strategy-stakeholder-engagemen/>

For any questions about Smart Data Research UK contact: deborah.kroll@esrc.ukri.org.

8. AOB

- Next DOG Meeting: 30 January 2024 13:30-15:00

Close.